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WHAT DOES IT MEAN TO USE A METHOD? THE ROLES OF METHODS FOR EXPERTS AND NOVICES DEALING WITH UNCERTAINTY: A QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Design is inherently uncertain. Therefore - aiming to support the designer - it is important to know how expert and novice designers deal with uncertainty. Historically, design methods have been proposed as a way for designers to solve complex and complicated problems systematically, thus reducing uncertainty. But do designers use methods like this? In this paper, we describe a study, which aimed to investigate how designers experience uncertainty in a design planning activity under time pressure. We assessed the design behavior of experts (more than 10 years of experience in practice) and advanced beginners (between 1 and 3 years of experience in practice). The results suggest that designers - novices and experts - articulate different purposes for the use of methods that go beyond the use of method as systematic instructions.

Keywords: use of methods, uncertainty, expertise

INTRODUCTION

Designing is inherently uncertain and complex - thus designers need to deal with both conditions. Methodology can be defined as means to support the designer when he or she is confronted with such uncertain and complex problems. For long, the main arguments for the need for methodological support were related to the difficulty - and partly - to the inability - of designers to deal with these ill-defined problems in an appropriate way. As Alexander (1964) specified:

“Today functional problems are becoming less simple all the time. But designers rarely confess

their inability to solve them. Instead, when a designer does not understand a problem clearly enough to find the order it really calls for, he falls back on some arbitrarily chosen formal order. The problem, because of its complexity, remains unsolved.” (p. 1).

In essence, systematic design methods are object- and context independent procedures that should support or allow the designer to systematically go through the steps of a design project deliberately. This assumption implies that the ideal way of working of the designer is a rational procedure. In this sense, a method is “essentially an instruction to carry out certain steps in a certain order” (Jensen and Andreasen, 2010, p.4). This choice for aiming to ‘rationalize’ designing is well illustrated by the advice of Hubka in his book “Principles of engineering design”: I advice against “relying on intuitive thought for present-day usage, even though this was the almost exclusive thought mode in the past” (Hubka, 1980, p. 28). At the same time it is to be seen that Hubka was very careful in making his claims. In the same chapter he wrote: “one cannot assume that design has always been viewed and represented in this way, nor can one assume that it will always remain in this form” (p. 27).

Thus, for a long time the dominant logic in design methodology has been that methods help designers structuring their activities. And in this sense methods are described as instructions to carry out defined steps in a described order. The underlying idea was of course that by *following* a systematic procedure the designer enhances the chances of ending up with a good solution.

In recent years this view of what it means to use a method has got been questioned to some extent: can the use of methods as systematic procedures be expected as 'natural design behavior' of the designer? Are methods used in this way? And if not, what *does* it mean to use a method?

CREATING SOCIAL ORDER

One way in which methods work differently has been studied recently by Jensen and Andreasen (2010). They argue that by taking an ethno-methodological approach will end up with a different view on what a method is. Design methods, the authors conclude, are about creating social order and are thus "the results of ongoing work, rather than the premises of it" (p. 4). Based on insights that students gathered in practice, their analysis shows that - at the least - methods are not necessarily *followed according the instructions*, but are often the product of social behavior aimed at creating social order.

HOW DO DESIGNERS DEAL WITH UNCERTAINTY?

We propose that in order to understand the need for - and use of - methods by designers we need to study the behaviour of designers in realistic environments. For example, how do designers respond to high time pressure or to the specific composition of the project team or to the introduction of new technology in a project? How do designers deal with communication problems in multidisciplinary teams? Such analyses should involve both, psychological theories and empirical investigations to understand how designers respond to the uncertainty of complex, wicked problems under time pressure.

In this paper we report about different ways in which designers dealt with such an activity. The research questions of the study were: How do expert and advanced beginners experience uncertainty in design planning and how do they deal with this? And what role do design methods play in this context?

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

DEALING WITH UNCERTAINTY

Anyone who acts must deal with uncertainty and particularly the act of designing requires from its practitioners to contend uncertainty. Uncertainty

relates to both, the perception of a situation and the consequences of an action. When meeting a situation each person develops expectancies that might be fulfilled or not; in the latter case this situation will cause surprise. Expectancies can be active (deliberate) or passive (intuitive). Active expectancies require conscious thoughts and draw on the limited capacity of attention. Intuitive perception and action work by either subconsciously processing information or by ignoring information (Gigerenzer and Brighton, 2009) and are practically effortless. Another distinction of expectancies relate to time: thus, temporary expectancies are related to priming and permanent expectancies function as mental model helping to make sense of ambiguous stimuli. Both mediate the large influence of context on our perception (Kahneman and Tversky, 1982). Preparing for specific events - e.g. while planning a design project - will have an active and a passive component. And for any situation "a proper balance must be achieved between a high level of specific readiness for the events that are most likely to occur and a general ability to respond appropriately when the unexpected happens" (Kahneman and Tversky, 1982, p. 2). This flexibility is relevant for designers during a design planning task as well.

In an empirical study Fricke (1993) has provided evidence for this assumption in the context of engineering design. He has shown that a flexible methodological approach - as opposed to either muddling through or strictly following a methodological structure - correlates with superior performance. However, design methods can have - but currently do not explicitly promote - a role at both sides of the balancing act. For long the dominant logic of design methodology has been to support designers by prescribing systematic structures. This conflicts with the use of methods in practice (Jensen and Andreasen, 2010). According to the model of variants of uncertainty of Kahneman and Tversky (1982) we propose that next to helping designers to prepare for events deliberately, there are other distinct functions that methods can play:

- Methods can help to prepare for events in a passive, over time. This is what is education aiming for during methodological training in design curricula for example.

- Methods can help in ‘priming’ designers just before or in the midst of activity. In complex situations, methods can help to make relevant details salient or keep an overview over many details. In this way methods can support the designers’ reasoning process in complex situations.
- Methods can help the designer responding to surprise. Reflection might be one effective way to react to surprise. Methods can provide support understanding a surprising event and adapting the designers’ mindset and intended approach along with an evolving understanding.

There is still little detailed understanding of the mechanisms in which methods work in these situations.

EXPERTISE AND NON-ROUTINE

The topic of design expertise has received increasing attention in design research and so in design literature (Cross, 2004). Experience is proven in many empirical studies in industry for having a major influence on the design process and thus on the result (Badke-Schaub and Frankenberger, 1999). The designers’ experience of past events, goals, motivation and beliefs form the lens through which he or she perceives the properties of the situation and develops solutions. It is important to note that this process is not necessarily accessible to conscious attention.

The quick immediate answer to a situation is a combination of two cognitive processes, ‘similarity matching’ and ‘frequency gambling’ (Reason, 1990). Similarity matching means that the situation at hand is automatically compared in regard to similarity to cases that are stored in memory. These cases are a combination of a specific situation and one or more corresponding responses - i.e. different ways to deal with this type of situation. As such, these intuitive responses will ‘compete’ with deliberate attempts to come up with an appropriate response. Particularly in similar situations this will lead to intuitive responses.

If, however, there is an element of newness to the situation this will get to the designers’ attention. The designer is required to consider his perception of

the current situation and perhaps even to adapt his routines to the elements of newness of the current situation. However, there is a threshold that might prevent him to start spending effort and time to reflect on how his intuitive approach should be adapted. The threshold to perform on a knowledge-based level (Rasmussen, 1983) and bypass routine behaviour will be determined partly by the available resources of the person - i.e. time, mental capacity, knowledge of the situation and possible actions, methods, motivation, confidence, etc. - and partly by the conditions of the situation at hand - i.e. risk of failure, impact of failure or success, social pressure, etc. If methods are to support designers in such conditions, we need to understand better how designers experience, and deal with these different influences on the person and the situation.

THE NEED FOR DESIGN METHODS

In situations that have a relatively high degree of newness - which is characteristic for many situations in design - it seems to be beneficial to draw attention to these characteristics (e.g. new type of problem, new discipline involved in the team, new technology involved, difficult client) and actively perceive and reason about them. Unfortunately, this will be at the expense of cognitive workload and time. And perhaps even more important; it will add uncertainty and doubts into the mind of the designer. Uncertainty about the accuracy of the perception and about the appropriateness of possible actions.

In dealing with those issues, methods could prove to be a valuable resource in choosing how to adapt routine responses to the newness of the situation at hand. For example, methods provide the designer with information about alternative pathways to solve the problem and could thus significantly lower the threshold for switching to active attention and thoughts about appropriate responses. Not only because it provides alternatives in the form of knowledge about appropriate actions, but also because it can reduce the perceived uncertainty that is experienced when making the switch. To be able to develop and transfer methods that support designers according to these issues, there is a need to understand designers’ behaviour in dealing with

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the experimental procedure. A standardized intervention took place at moment (1) after which the participants sent their intermediate results at moment (2). Critical feedback was given to the participants at moment (3).

uncertainty in the design arena and in the role design methods can play.

RESEARCH APPROACH

The aim of this paper is to better understand which elements influence the use of methods in design. How do different designers experience uncertainty during a particular design activity? What role do methods play for the designer when coping with uncertainty? In this study, we have analyzed how designers experienced uncertainty in a complex design planning task, when they used methods, and the tried to analyze the possible reasons for using methods.

DESIGN PLANNING

Design planning is a generic activity in the early phases of an innovation project and involves the staging of a process that is characterized by complexity and unpredictability. Furthermore, it seems that design planning is also an activity, which is particularly susceptible for methodological support. We can expect that the one that is planning the project is mainly thinking about process elements. For more information about the planning task, we refer to Daalhuizen and Badke-Schaub (2010).

SET-UP OF THE STUDY

Expert and advanced beginners were asked to create an approach and a planning procedure for a complex task based on a fictitious design brief under high time pressure. The participants were first introduced to the workspace and could familiarize themselves

with using the methods database. Any technical question regarding the use of the database was offered to be answered at this point. After familiarization, the design brief was presented and the deadline for delivering the final result was announced (105 minutes). During the accomplishment of the task a standardized intervention was introduced by a hypothetical project manager (the client) to increase the level of perceived uncertainty (see figure 1, at '1'). The participants were requested to produce a presentation of their approach and planning in PowerPoint (indicated with '2' in figure 1). After that submission, they received criticism on specific points of their intermediate results ('3' in figure 1). The participants then finished their project proposal until the time of the deadline. Materials to create the proposal including paper, pencils, sticky notes and a laptop with Microsoft PowerPoint were provided right from the start.

SELECTION OF PARTICIPANTS

The experts were industrial designers with more than 10 years of experience in practice. The advanced beginners had 1 to 3 years of experience in practice. We confirmed all designers had a background in methodological design to ensure familiarity with using methods in design.

The details of the sample that participated in the study on the use of methods are reported in Daalhuizen and Badke-Schaub (2010). For the study reported here, 2 experts and 1 novice were taken

from a sample of 17 designers for detailed analysis. The selection was made based on:

- Frequency of utterances that referred to the usage or role of methods
- A variation according to the two distinct profiles of designers was chosen for the purpose of the in-depth analysis: fluctuating vs. stable patterns of arousal and confidence.
- The chosen designers should have used methods during the execution of the task.

METHOD DATABASE

An interactive database of design methods was available for use and included more than 100 methods from various sources (Boeijen, et al. 2009; Cross, 1989; IDEO, 2003; Pahl and Beitz, 1995). The methods ranged from phase-models, e.g. VDI 2221 (VDI, 1993) and the Basic Design Cycle (Roozenburg and Eekels, 1995) to small-scale methods such as the IDEO method cards (IDEO, 2003). The database provided a basic navigation menu to access the methods. The database was used to create a condition of high availability and usability of design methods during the task, i.e. to lower the threshold for using methods. Furthermore the database allowed the participants to access a description of a method within 2 to 3 clicks of the mouse. It was explicitly mentioned at the start of the experiment that the use of the database was *optional* for completing the task successfully.

METHOD HELPDESK

In addition a methods-helpdesk was available for help with searching and applying methods from the database via a chat program (MSN messenger). The helpdesk allowed participants to seek support for searching and applying methods. A research assistant familiar with the contents of the database responded to questions of the participants.

METHOD USAGE

In this study we were specifically interested in the use of methods by designers with two distinct profiles. We therefore selected only participants that used methods during the study. Method usage was determined by focusing at two factors:

- The participants looked at methods in the database.
- The participants explicitly mentioned the method in the end result.

SUBJECTIVE STATE DURING THE EXPERIMENT

At defined moments during the experiment, the participants were asked to report their emotional arousal, their feeling of control, their confidence in the intermediate result and their perceived time pressure. These questions were asked

- Before the start of the intervention ('1' in figure 1),
- After the intervention,
- After the participants had handed in the intermediate result to the project manager ('2' in figure 1),
- After the critical feedback ('3' in figure 1),
- At the end of the exercise.

Measuring subjective arousal: The SAM technique

The Self-Assessment Manikin (SAM) is a non-verbal pictorial assessment technique that directly measures pleasure, arousal, and dominance associated with a person's affective reaction to a wide variety of stimuli (Bradley and Lang, 1994; see Lang, Bradley and Cuthbert, 1997 for instructions on how to use the technique).

Participants are asked to report their level of happiness, excitement and feeling of being in control of (dominant over) a situation. Pleasure, arousal, and dominance are pervasive in organizing human judgments for a wide range of perceptual and symbolic stimuli (Bradley and Lang, 1994).

Measuring confidence and time pressure

The perceived level of confidence and time pressure was measured by a short questionnaire. The participants were asked to rate each time on a Likert scale from one of five:

- To what extend they understand the task.
- How confident they are about the current concept for the planning.
- To what extend they know how to proceed.
- To what extend they are considering alternative approaches.

- To what extent they expect to be able to finish the task on time.
- To what extent they expected to be able to check the quality of the result before the deadline.

Performance

The participants were selected from a sample of seventeen participants used in an earlier study (Daalhuizen and Badke-Schaub, 2010). The performance measures were taken from the same study.

In the following we report the analyses of the procedure of three designers, Roger and Sean with high experience and Pierce with low experience.

EXPERT DESIGNER 1: ROGER

Roger is an expert industrial designer with a background in systematic design from the Technical University. He has more than 10 years of experience in design practice.

Figure 2. Ratings of the designer Roger for the three dimensions happiness, excitement and control over the five moments in time during the experiment.

Emotion and control - A fluctuating pattern

The graphs in figure 2 show fluctuating levels of the three variables happiness, excitement and control on the positive part of the scale till almost half of the time. Over the entire time of the experiment the participant feels quite happy, what indicates that the level of arousal was experienced as positive. The graph shows that the 'level of excitement' started at a very high level and dropped during the execution of the task. The level of control fluctuated most; it started high and increased in the first phase (before the intervention). After the intervention - when the

critical feedback was received - the experienced level of control dropped to a low level. Towards the end of the experiment, the level of control increased again but stayed very low.

Confidence - Decreasing confidence

Roger reports a decreasing level of confidence in his work throughout the task execution (see figure 3). This is not caused by a poor understanding of the task since Erik reports a steadily growing understanding of the task after initial analysis. Next to that, Roger reports an increasing awareness of how to proceed next, but a decreasing consideration of alternative approaches.

Figure 3. Roger reports a steadily decreasing confidence in spite of a good understanding of the task, unstable yet increasing clarity about how to proceed and decreasing tendency to consider alternative approaches.

Time pressure - high level

After an initial phase of analyzing the brief, the level of perceived time pressure remained constantly high.

Figure 4. After a proper understanding of the task was achieved time pressure was reported to be constantly high.

USE OF METHODS

During the planning activity, the expert applied 4 methods in his end-result. These methods were *rapid ethnography*, *competitive product survey*, *probes* and *brainstorming*.

Using methods to reason about the own procedure

Early on, Roger wonders if there are methods that can help him achieving an important sub-goal that he has identified: understanding the target group's triggers for trusting a complex, medical product intended for use at home. He is using a number of user-centered design methods to reason about which approach is most suitable for the goal and situation at hand. And he is using them to reason about his initial requirements for the method. While doing this he is continuously adapting his own approach. It seems that the purpose of using methods in this case is to be able to consider all kinds of (alternative) aspects of his goal, the situation and potential approach:

"A core question is how can the packaging communicate trust in the retail environment (...) If there is a technique for that, that would be welcome in this phase. So I am going to ask the method helpdesk: is there a low-threshold technique - in terms of lead-time - to understand consumer trust?"

After a response from the method helpdesk, he seems to be search for further information while browsing through the method database:

"For the fun of it, let's have a look if there is something about personas, or a day in the life of... (...) Collage, cultural probes. We don't have time for that. Here is the extreme user interview. I found it"

Apparently Roger had already some methods in mind for which he was looking in the database. However, he doesn't want to use what he has found and starts reconsidering his initial goal:

"Looking at the time... Extreme user interviews... let's see. I don't really believe in doing interview. Actually, we want to go to the people at their home. We want... a more ethnographic approach to learn to understand people. But that takes a lot of time."

He starts searching further and finds a method that seems to fit his adapted requirements:

"What else do we got? This one I like. Competitive product survey. This one I find interesting"

He reads the description of the method and starts reasoning how he might go about executing the method so that it fits the relevant characteristics of the project:

"This is what I am going to do (...) And then I will invite a number of people from the target Group. I will display a number of products, en I let those people talk about it. If it is necessary I will guide it into the direction of: what do you think about them? (...) in short, what are the triggers of trust? I am going to do that in a Group session. And I am going to use the target Group. I am going to try to find people that already have purchased the product..."

Using a method to convince the client

Later on, Roger is preparing the final presentation of his project planning. At this point, he is considering the contents of the presentation and is deliberating how to present a phase he calls 'user context research'. In this case, Roger chose the method to impress the audience of his presentation. He starts looking for a method that sounds convincing:

"I am going to look into this [database] to see if there is a good name for this. I often use my own names for things [methods] for which more fancy official names exist"

He finds a name that inspires him:

"Behavioral archeology. That sounds nice. Rapid ethnography. That is more or less what we... [reads description of method]. That is nice. We are going to use that (...) I am going to use 'rapid ethnography' as a catch phrase"

SUMMARY

Analyzing the way in which Roger reacted to the design problem and the availability of methods, we can see that he started with a positive mind-set, excited by the task, and open to try new methods. During the execution he was browsing through the database quite frequently to consider different methods. However, analyzing the design behavior over time, we can see a decreasing excitement and confidence. Apparently, his feeling of competence went down, and this might have affected his performance. When compared to the other participants of the study (Daalhuizen and Badke-

Schaub, 2010) Roger ranks 12th out of 17, in terms of performance. It seems that the very open attitude towards trying new methods in this time pressured, complex task was not very supportive for his performance.

EXPERT DESIGNER 2: SEAN

Sean is an expert industrial designer with a background in systematic design at a Technical University. He has more than 10 years of experience in design practice.

Emotion and control - A stable pattern

The graphs in figure 5 show relatively stable levels of happiness, excitement and control. Sean reports both a low level of happiness and excitement at the beginning of the experiment. These factors increase steadily towards the end of the task. It seems that Sean experienced only a moderate level of positive arousal. He also seems to be quite indifferent concerning the intervention.

Figure 5. . Ratings of the designer Sean for the three dimensions happiness, excitement and control over the five moments in time during the experiment. Sean reports a stable pattern, with a slight increase for all three factors.

Confidence - Slowly increasing

During the task execution, Sean’s confidence in the intermediate result steadily rises. At the same time he gets more confident how to proceed and how he will continue. The intervention does not seem to have a negative influence on his confidence. Furthermore, Sean is considering alternative approaches.

Figure 6. Sean reports a steadily increasing level of confidence along with an increasing understanding of the task and clarity about how to proceed. Surprisingly, he also reports an increasing consideration of alternative approaches.

Time pressure - high level

The reported level of time pressure is high. During the whole activity, Sean reports that he does not expect to finish his work entirely, or check for u

Figure 7. Sean reports a constantly high time pressure.

USE OF METHODS

During the planning activity, Sean applies 5 methods arriving at his end-result. These methods are *trend analysis, vision in product design, brainstorming, product concept evaluation* and *Harris profile*.

Searching methods for an ‘initial start’

After reading the brief, Sean reflects of how to approach the design brief. He does not state a specific goal, but starts by asking the method helpdesk for suggestion. His aim seems to be using the methods as initial start as ‘sparking off’ an initial idea for his planning. Sean does not search with a specific target in mind, but just ‘browse’ and hope to come across something interesting:

“Do you know which method is appropriate for studying values of products for a specific target group?”

His query is rather broad and apparently, Andre does not have a specific goal in mind:

“For now I am looking for methods across the board. So methods with and without input from the user in the design process. Just give some suggestions”

The helpdesk responds by saying:

“You can have a look at Human Centered methods. Here you will find methods that are appropriate to learn from users and to include the user on the design process. An appropriate method might be ‘Competitive Product Survey’”

To which Sean replies:

“Thanks, any other tips for methods?”

Threshold: Learning curve of methods

Later on during the design process, Sean considered a number of methods that he found in the database, or that were suggested to him by the helpdesk. But he does not feel confident using them. Although he blames the manager for this, it became obvious that the use of new methods would have increased his uncertainty and therefore he preferred to avoid using a new method:

“What I find difficult is that I am not familiar with all those concepts [referring to the methods in the database] and that it will take too much time to study all those methods. So I am afraid some completeness and systematic work would get lost. Because of the time pressure. So I am tempted to just leave the methods alone and just make a planning without any theory or help from others. And to see what I can fit into it later on”

He points to the hypothetical project manager as a cause for this situation. He expects that a manager has done some of the reading into potential methods to prepare for the project:

“Concerning this, I cannot relate to the manager in this situation because I expect that a manager would read into the topic in advance”

If we take into account the broadness of his previous search, the threshold to use unfamiliar methods might additionally be caused by the lack of a clear goal.

SUMMARY

Analyzing the way in which Sean has dealt with the planning task, we see that he starts off with a low level of excitement and happiness. He does not seem to have an initial idea how to start. Although he tries to use the method database and helpdesk for inspiration he reports a tendency to avoid using unfamiliar methods from the database. However, during the exercise, excitement and happiness increase and confidence in the intermediate results rise along. The methods that were applied were added at the end of the exercise, after Sean has developed his own approach. This strategy increased his performance, and he ranked as 5th out of 17 participants in the original study.

NOVICE DESIGNER 1: PIERCE

Pierce is an advanced beginner in industrial design with a background in systematic design at a Technical University. He has about 2 years of experience in design practice.

Emotion and control - A fluctuating pattern

The graph in figure 8 shows that Pierce reported a fluctuating level of excitement and happiness during the exercise. He started only moderately excited, and happy. He seems to experience the whole task as being out of his control. Pierce reported to be influenced by the intervention quite strongly.

Figure 8. Pierce shows a fluctuating level of excitement and happiness at the lower part of the scale. Dropping quite dramatically at the time of the intervention feedback on his intermediate results. The level of control remains stable at a low level until the end of the task.

CONFIDENCE - A FLUCTUATING PATTERN

During the task execution, Pierce's confidence in the intermediate result fluctuates (see figure 9). It drops, rises again and drops after the intervention

with feedback. At the same time, his understanding of the task rises, and is probably not the reason for his fluctuating level of confidence. Pierce reports that his clarity of how to proceed changes at each point - however he does not seem to consider alternative approaches. The reported low level of control and fluctuating clarity on how to proceed, explain his unstable level of confidence.

Figure 9. Pierce reports a fluctuating level of confidence during the task execution. At the same time, the understanding of the task increases but the clarity about how to proceed remains unstable.

TIME PRESSURE - UNSTABLE & HIGH

Pierce reports a high and unstable level of time pressure (figure 10).

Figure 10. Pierce reports an unstable but mainly high time pressure.

USE OF METHODS

During the assignment, Pierce used 3 methods to arrive at the end result. These were *vision in product design*, *focus groups* and *goal clarification*.

Browsing through methods

From the start of the exercise, Pierce browses regularly through the database. Apparently, the availability of many different methods allows him to think of, and compare alternative approaches to the task at hand. While browsing, he recognizes a number of methods:

“these kind of methods I already picked up during my time at the university. Nowadays during a project I do things more intuitively”

But he also mentions that the high availability of methods though the database could have an impact on his consideration of methods:

“If I would have this at home [the database], and I would be bored a bit, I would start browsing”

Later on, during a new browsing session - and after analyzing the brief, he states that he has now a number of things that need to be done, and starts looking for appropriate methods:

“I now have a list of all kinds of things that I might want to do. So now I will browse which methods I can use. Many of them do not fit the packaging design”

Eventually, Pierce is triggered by one method that he sees and recognizes. He decides to use it (see also the next section).

Method as a stepping stone for a detailed approach

At some point Pierce starts browsing through the database again. After some time he arrives at a page where the *Vision in Product Design* method is described and Pierce decides to use it. He then proceeds by considering which steps to include, and how to implement the method in detail, beyond the description of the method in the database. This method seems to have the purpose of a stepping stone for thinking about the details of his approach. Pierce seems to ‘play’ with the steps described in the method based on his requirements or ideas for the project.

“I think I am going to... The ViP method [vision in product design] is a nice method. Particularly the part of the context... Maybe this part I leave out [points to first steps in the method]. But it is nice to think about the future context...”

He plans to skip a number of steps of the method. After he has made this decision, Pierce starts detailing the method:

“Maybe we can have multiple themes... in that context. So we do research into the users and technological possibilities. And part is sustainability. And we are going to do that qualitatively”

SUMMARY

After starting with the design problem Pierce's excitement and happiness drop dramatically, yet from the start he is very open to browse through, and consider methods from the database. His confidence and perception of time pressure vary during the exercise and he changes his mind about how obvious his next steps are to him. It seems that he does not feel competent in coping with the given planning problem. Considering that Pierce is still a novice, this does not seem surprising.

IN terms of performance he reached a good result. He ranks 6th out of 17 participants.

CONCLUSIONS

Designers perceive and experience the same design problem differently right from the beginning. They feel excited or less excited, they understand and know what to do next and feel confident or they don't know about their further proceeding.

Accordingly they use methods for a variety of purposes. From the analyses of how 3 industrial designers dealt with a complex, design planning task under time pressure it can be hypothesized that the possible benefits of the use of methods can be much broader than only providing instructions for dealing with the problem at hand. This seems to go beyond the traditional role of methods as instructions for systematic procedures, confirming and adding to recent work by Jensen and Andreasen (2010).

The designers had to deal with a high level of uncertainty, which was even increased through the introduction of a standardized intervention which assured that - independent from the level of experience - all participants had to cope with a non-routine situation. According to the analyses of the three cases reported in this paper we derived different purposes for using methods. We have found evidence that methods can be used as medium of communication to the external world, i.e. the client or project manager but in the same way methods can be used to guide the designer's reasoning process about the own procedure. Methods are used to get a first inspiration how to deal with the problem; they provide a first idea what might be a suitable way how to deal with the problem at hand. Methods are used to specify the goal.

Using a method to communicate with the client: external justification of the own procedure

Methods are used to convince others of the quality of the own work by pointing to the benefits and/or necessity of a systematic approach. Exposing the own procedure by referring to a method, is one way how the designer might be able to account for his procedure (in hindsight and in planning for the future). The uncertainty of the problem seems to be solved; at least there is a feeling of shared understanding between client and designer about the 'how' to deal with the problem without talking about the 'what'. Thus, the designer's certainty about the further procedure provides a trustful climate and the designer might even gain more time and freedom to think about the 'what'.

Using a method to enhance the structure and to provide an overview of the own procedure

In the case of complex projects - multiple stakeholders and interests, many interdependent factors, complex technology, etc. - methods are used to enhance the reasoning process by gaining a structured overview. Analyzing and comparing descriptions of different methods, necessary steps become salient and can be made explicit. Furthermore, by considering the implications of a specific method, requirements, restrictions and boundary conditions of the project become clearer to the designer. This might allow the designer to structure the problem and keep an overview especially in the moment where he needs to go more into details.

Using a method as stepping-stone

A method can be used as stepping stone for a complex and uncertain design problem. A method can inspire a designer to pursuit a specific approach (e.g. developing a design vision before starting to define requirements and developing concepts). The method can then serve as a stepping-stone for preparing a customized approach that fits the project at hand. As a consequence, the designer can

develop an approach that is grounded in a formalized method, yet fits the project and situation - and the designer!

Using a method to clarify a goal

In the light of a vague defined goal, methods are used to consider alternative procedures to achieve or redefine the goal. By comparing alternatives, the designer can consider what consequences different approaches would have in terms of the further procedure and the influence on the end result. These if-then scenarios might help the designer to imagine what he would like or not like to achieve. As a consequence, the project's goals become clearer.

DISCUSSION

In this study we showed that designers point to different purposes for using a method. But as we have analyzed only three designers, working on one design problem, it is obvious that the different reasons do not make up an extensive list. Furthermore, we cannot draw conclusions as to the frequency of occurrence or importance of the different roles in practice in education. However, it does show that the use of methods can go beyond a role as instructions for following a systematic procedure.

Of course, this specific research setting also has some limitations. First, the experimental setting itself is an affordance which might have influenced the behavior of the designers. Second, the design brief does not involve designing activity itself. Finally, the way the methods were provided and arranged seems crucial in determining their actual usage. The database used in this study provided a low threshold for the participants. Browsing and comparing methods could be done quickly and easily. And - we assume- this kind of facilitation influenced the designers' tendency using methods in a positive way.

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